

MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE CHEST AND SPINAL DISC IN EXPERIMENTAL DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract. *In the sternocostal complex of the generation born from rats pharmacologically corrected with actropid during pregnancy, morphological changes in the bone-costal-ligament structures differ significantly from the morphological picture of the TCC of the untreated generation of rats, closer to the normative levels of formation, deep irreversible changes are revealed, reflecting developmental delays, i.e. dysplasia.*

Keywords: *sternocostal complex, diabetes mellitus, rats, dysplasia.*

Relevance. It is important to suggest that the growth and rapid prevalence of diabetes mellitus pose a real threat worldwide. According to data, more than 422 million patients worldwide suffer from diabetes, of which more than 199 million are women. The number of women with diabetes is expected to reach 313 million by 2040. Two out of five women with diabetes (more than 60 million) are of reproductive age. Diabetes is the ninth leading cause of death in women worldwide: 2.1 million women die from diabetes every year. Women with type 1 diabetes have an increased risk of premature miscarriage or the birth of a child with malformations. There are significant scientific studies in the literature aimed at diagnosing the extent of the impact of CT disease on the body, new treatment methods, organizing appropriate rehabilitation processes and especially predicting complications that may be observed [6, 7, 8, 10].

However, the processes of formation in the body, in the organs and systems of children born to mothers with BD, especially the development and growth of the skeletal system, are described in a number of scientific publications. When determining the process of growth of the child's chest, the obvious evaluation criterion is the indicators of the bones of the chest and spine [1, 2, 3, 9]. Based on this, it is important to determine the state of chest deformities, assess their relationship with the quality of life and, based on this, develop new approaches to the primary prevention of chest deformities in these children.

Taking into account the above, it should be suggested that the issue of creating a system for improving preventive measures aimed at early diagnosis and elimination of morphofunctional changes in the sternocostal system and its morphofunctional changes under the influence of diabetes mellitus in the prenatal period is considered relevant and is practically important in fundamental medicine.

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the morphological growth and dynamics of development of the bones of the sternocostal complex under the influence of experimental diabetes mellitus at the stages of postnatal ontogenesis.

Research methods. The study used macroscopic, histological, histochemical, morphometric and statistical methods of analysis.

Materials and methods of research. The material of the study is the sternocostal complex. The object of the study are 44 white outbred rats weighing 150-200 grams.

The effect of experimental diabetes mellitus on the formation of the sternocostal complex during postnatal ontogenesis was studied. Macroscopic, microscopic, morphological and morphometric methods of research were used.

Discussion and results. For the purpose of comparative scientific analysis of the results of the main study, the morphological manifestations of the sternocostal complex in the offspring of control rats were analyzed in pre-planned observation periods, respectively, and the observed dynamic changes were studied in them.

Laboratory animals were divided into two groups. Group I consisted of 9 female rats selected for control. Group II included 25 experimental animals (females).

The animals of the experimental group were administered a mixture of alloxan 150 mg / kg together with distilled water 15 ml into the abdominal cavity by a single intraperitoneal injection. Female rats were fasted for 24 hours according to the standard before the injection. After that, the average weight of female rats when measuring the weight of each was 150-200 grams.

In our experiment, the state of convulsions in animals was observed 15 minutes after the administration of alloxan. Between 5-7 hours, bruises on the tails were observed, and during the next 24-48 hours, signs of a strong increased need for water, polyuria, mild tremors and tachycardia were observed. Rats in the control and experimental group were measured for normal blood glucose levels. The calculated blood glucose level is 350 mg / dl (plus Satellite. Russia) that confirms hyperglycemia.

Surprisingly, young rats born from pregnant rats in the control and experimental groups for the experiment 14-, 21-, 30-, 45-, 60-were taken under control in the daytime periods.

Experimental young rats were first placed in a special container in accordance with the rules of etiquette, anesthetized with chloroform and fixed on the guillotine equipment, laying them on their backs. The prepared sections were stained by the Van Gieson and hematoxylin-eosin methods to study the structure of connective tissue, as well as by the Masson method to study connective tissue, cells and their intermediate elements, and the histochemical reaction was carried out by the Schick methods. The finished micro preparations were viewed under a SARRL Zeiss Microcopy GmbH microscope and photographed with an Axio Lab. A1 camera (Germany).

Besides that, for the purpose of comparative scientific analysis of the results of the main study, for the first time in the pre-planned observation periods, the morphological manifestations of the sternocostal complex in the offspring of the control rats were analyzed, respectively, and the observed dynamic changes were studied in them.

Initially, the histological examination of the sternocostal complex for morphological studies at the junction of the cartilaginous parts of the rib with the sternum showed that in the control individual, ossification of the cartilaginous part of the rib begins from the sternal end, which corresponds to the observation period (Fig. 1)

During this period, symmetrical basophilicity of the sternum cartilage along the ossification line, relative intensity of proximal ossification, chaotic formation of gaps in bone columns, uneven distribution of the proliferative cartilaginous layer and an abundance of fat pads in the space of the surrounding soft tissues were observed in the animals of the experimental group (Fig. 2)

While examining the sternum tissue on the 14th day of observation in the control individual, at the junction of the rib with the sternum, linear differentiation begins from the periphery, in the matrix of the cartilage, roughness is revealed along the periphery. It was found that the membrane above the cartilage is thinned, the sternum-costal angle is relatively thickened.

Additionally, the results of morphological studies at the early stages of postnatal ontogenesis in the dynamics of growth of the sternocostal complexes in control individuals showed that they affect the dynamic change in the mechanism of development of the sternum in the mother's offspring during pregnancy and lactation. On the 21st day of observation, synchondrosis appears in the cartilaginous tissues of the 4th growth zone of the sternum and in the places of attachment of the ribs. By the 30th day, the transitional tissues in all four growth zones have the same architecture.

Figure 1. The chest of the control animal (day 14) shows engorgement of the chest, ossification corresponds to the observation period; G.E., K 200.

Figure 2. The chest of the control animal in the 21-day period shows engorgement of the chest, ossification corresponds to the observation period; G.E., K. 200

What is more important to suggest that the tube is separated from the bone growth zones on both sides (proximal and distal) by the same mechanism of bone formation. The control group - isogenic chondrocytes, in the early stages (14th day) are located chaotically, singly, in pairs, in the

following periods (21-30 days) small isogenic groups of 3-4 cells of different sizes on average are observed.

Figure 3. Sternum of a 30-day-old rat, proximal (upper) growth plate. OK. G.E. K.400.

The shape of these chondrocytes is elliptical or cylindrical, in some places rounded cells are found. In the following periods (45 -, 60 days) in chondrocytes there is a spherical or rounded nucleus surrounded by cytoplasm. The growth zone is represented by proliferative cells, which are located columnarly and contain up to 10-12 cells in each column. These chondrocytes differ from neighboring columns by a clear set of fibrils directed longitudinally along the layers of the main substance of the matrix. Mitotic patterns were found in some chondrocytes of this zone. Single cases of mitosis process were revealed in rats of the main group.

CONCLUSION

By summarizing of the above-mentioned ideas, it should be suggested that the following conclusions were made:

1. Under the conditions of diabetes mellitus of the expectant mother's body, the greatest changes in rat pups occur in the tissue of the vestibule of the growth zones, it becomes significantly thinner and the number of cells in it decreases.
2. It was experimentally established that significant changes in mineral metabolism and ossification markers in the sexually mature generation, caused by the adverse effects of diabetes mellitus during pregnancy, are more pronounced in the later (30-45 days) observation periods.

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